

Development of a Hardware-in-the-Loop vehicle traction control using Machine learning techniques for embedded systems

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Abstract - This work aims to describe the design of an ECU using a 32 bits microcontroller STM32H743ZIT6, for use in a traction control system in HiL mode to control two BLDC wheels of a hybrid vehicle. The data used to train the algorithm were obtained through simulation software Carsim® in conjunction with mathematical software Matlab/Simulink®. The controller was developed using Machine Learning technique and used a 3-layer LSTM network working in the embedded system of ECU to control the traction of the vehicle.

Key-Words: Embedded System; Hardware-in-the-Loop; Machine Learning; Simulated Vehicle; Traction Control.

INTRODUCTION

The primary function of traction control is to prevent wheel lockup during acceleration. In vehicles with internal combustion engines, traction control is implemented using wheel sensors that detect when the car loses traction. These systems employ ABS brakes, electronic fuel injection, and throttle control to regulate the power sent to the wheels (1). In internal combustion vehicles, the differential, which ensures that the wheels have the correct speeds when the vehicle is turning, is mechanical in nature (2).

In electric vehicles (EVs) and hybrid vehicles (HEVs), the differential system is no longer composed solely of mechanical components such as crown gears, pinions, and planetary gears. Instead, the mechanical differential must work in conjunction with the speed control of the electric motors. This integrated differential is known as an electronic differential.

The advantage of electronic differentials over mechanical ones is that the speed of each wheel can be controlled and measured with greater precision, enhancing vehicle maneuverability at high speeds and significantly improving performance and safety during operation (3).

In this context, this work aims to develop an AI traction control system for use in a hybrid vehicle to control the power train composed of two BLDC motors connected directly to the vehicle's rear wheels. The data used to train the algorithm were obtained through simulation software Carsim® in conjunction with mathematical software Matlab/Simulink®. The controller was developed using Machine Learning technique and uses a 3-layer LSTM network working in the embedded system of ECU to control the traction of a vehicle using a 32bits microcontroller STM32H743ZIT6 in connection with two stages of 3-phase N-FET MOSFET's full bridge to control both motors. The ECU has many inputs to get feedback from the motor, like current sensors connected at each motor, hall sensor, CAN, and USB interfaces to communicate with the vehicle and simulator respectively. To validate the efficiency of the traction control and the ECU hardware developed both in the simulated environment and the operation of the two BLDC motors connected to the hardware, the Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) technique was employed.

HiL simulation involves connecting an ECU or Control Hardware to a simulation system that emulates real-world conditions, allowing the ECU to operate as if in a

real system (4). This technique is applied during the final validation phase of an ECU, after MiL and SiL tests. Previous work used commercial platforms like myRIO and Labview for HiL ABS testing (5) (6), while this study innovates by developing dedicated microcontroller-based hardware to control the system.

Figure 1 presents an overview of the vehicle used as the object of study, indicating the controlled variables, the logical blocks that describe the subsystems, and the interaction between them. Figure 2 shows the electronic and mechanical components that make up the vehicle, where the rear vehicle traction consists of two axial motors mounted directly on the wheels.

Figure 1. Blocks comprising the Traction Subsystem.

Figure 2. Configuration of the light urban HEV with indication of components and connections.

DEVELOPMENT

The development of the control system will be presented in two sections: software and hardware. The software section will cover the method used for simulation, data col-

lection, network modeling, and solution implementation. The hardware section will present the hardware blocks, control structure, sizing, embedded code implementation, and the connection of the motors to the board.

Software

The traction control implemented in the vehicle used a Machine Learning technique, where the data used for training the network was obtained through simulations performed in the vehicle simulator CarSim[®]. The car model used in all simulations was a generic Class C Hatchback with front Strut suspension and rear 5-Link suspension as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Configuration of class C vehicle in Carsim

To determine the input and output variables of the system, the correlation between these variables and the vehicle's traction, as well as their availability in the real environment, were considered. The following variables were used as system inputs:

Vehicle speed (Km/h), individual wheel speed (Km/h), required torque (N/m), system torque (N/m), and steering wheel angle (deg).

The output variables of the network are Beta and A_y . For the development of the 3-layer LSTM network, the libraries Numpy, Pandas, TensorFlow, and Scikit-learn in Python were used within the Colab[®] environment.

The electronic differential control block resulting from the TCS follows a structure similar to that developed by (7), however, the Fuzzy logic used by the author was replaced by the Machine Learning block in this work. Figure 4 shows the view of the differential block designed.

Figure 4. Block diagram of the electronic differential control system

The data obtained in the simulation were converted into a CSV file, which was used as a dataset for training and testing the designed network. The LSTM neural network was chosen due to its memory persistence from previous decisions and its suitability for use with time series.

The fundamental equation of a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network can be summarized as:

$$h_t = LSTM(x_t, h_{t-1}, C_{t-1}) \quad (1)$$

Where h_t is the current hidden state, x_t is the current input, h_{t-1} is the previous hidden state, and C_{t-1} is the previous cell state (8).

Table 1 provides a summary of the developed neural network model architecture, specifying the layers, their output shapes, and the total number of parameters.

Table 1. Model Architecture Summary

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_layer_2 (InputLayer)	(None, 10, 9)	0
lstm_6 (LSTM)	(None, 10, 100)	44,000
lstm_7 (LSTM)	(None, 10, 100)	80,400
lstm_8 (LSTM)	(None, 100)	80,400
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 2)	202
Total params		205,002
Trainable params		205,002
Non-trainable params		0

After model training, the network was converted to TensorFlow Lite format and incorporated into the micro-controller hardware. The hardware communicates via a serial COM interface at 115200Bps with the simulator, receiving data from the simulation, driving the BLDC motors connected to the power interface, reading current and Hall sensors, calculating the speed and torque of the wheels, and sending control variables to the simulated environment, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. System in HiL configuration

Figure 6 shows the Simulink blocks connected to provide the interface between the Hardware and the Simulator. In this way, the environment runs in a Hil control loop.

Figure 6. Overview of Simulink blocks of control

Hardware

The hardware developed was designed exclusively for the project, using the STM32H743ZIT6, Arm-7 micro-controller operating at 480 MHz. The board has two power branches, one dedicated to BLDC motors, capable of operating up to 100V_{DC} and the main power supply that allows the hardware to be powered in a range of 15V_{DC} to 35V_{DC}. Communication interfaces include USB, CAN, I²C, and UART. The power stage has two three-phase bridges with N-channel MOSFETs in TO-252-3 and DPAK packages, allowing the use of various MOSFET models with V_{DS} ratings up to 120V_{DC}@90A continuous to control BLDC motors. Figure 7 shows the block configuration of the board.

Figure 7. Overview of hardware blocks composition

The Firmware implementation uses the previous NN trained in Python, was developed in C language, using STCubeTool®.

The hardware can operate one or two motors running at the same time. Figure 8 shows the hardware connected to a 500W BLDC hubby motor operating in HiL configuration.

Figure 8. Hardware connected in HiL mode

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This paper addressed the development of a traction control system using advanced machine learning techniques in a HiL simulation environment. The system is implemented in an ECU based on the 32-bit STM32H743ZIT6 microcontroller, which controls two BLDC motors connected to the rear wheels of a hybrid vehicle. The 3-layer LSTM neural network was trained with data obtained from simulations in CarSim®, integrated with Matlab/Simulink®, to ensure that the control was adjusted to the real conditions of the vehicle.

The control strategy based on neural networks was embedded in the ECU system, enabling real-time communication with the simulation system and the operation of the BLDC motors, allowing HiL operation. This work contributes to the innovation of HiL platforms for vehicle part simulation in the national context, as it creates proprietary hardware, eliminating the need for integrated platforms for its operation, representing an innovation compared to the works of (5) and (6) in this regard.

The hardware is capable of operating in HiL (Hardware in the Loop) the BLDC motors while providing the processed data to the simulator. In an objective view, the development was considered successful. The control system developed was able to prevent the loss of traction in the simulated scenarios. Figure 9 shows the vehicle ma-

king a turn in one of the simulated scenarios using the control in HiL.

Figure 9. Vehicle controlled by the Hardware in the HiL mode.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the predictions made by the model, it was assessed in three scenarios: Double Lane 100K/h, Rollover Steer Input, and S-Turn w/ Clothoids. Figures 10a, 11a, 12a present the predictions made by the model for the variable Beta concerning the actual value and Figures 10b, 11b, and 12b present the predictions made by the model for the variable Ay concerning the actual value.

(a) Actual Beta vs Predicted (b) Actual Ay vs Predicted
Figure 10. Double Lane 100Km/h

(a) Actual Beta vs Predicted (b) Actual Ay vs Predicted
Figure 11. Rollover Steer Input

(a) Actual Beta vs Predicted (b) Actual Ay vs Predicted
Figure 12. S-Turn w/ Clothoids

Table 2 presents the error indices obtained in the different scenarios.

Table 2. Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE).

Condição (type)	MSE	MAE
Double Lane 100Km/h	0.0659	0.140
Rollover Steer Input	1.165	0.664
S-Turn w/ Clothoids	0.248	0.287

Analyzing Figures 10a, 11a, 12a, 10b, 11b, and 12b, it can be observed that the model can predict the variable A_y more accurately compared to Beta in all tested scenarios. By examining the errors indicated in Table 2, it can be seen that the MSE and MAE errors are substantially lower for the Double Lane 100Km/h scenario compared to the other scenarios. This indicates that the model exhibits overfitting for this particular test scenario. This discrepancy could be attributed to a series of factors, such as the quality of the data, the distribution of the test data concerning the training data, the complexity of the model, the configuration of the hyperparameters, the normalization of the data, and the relevance of the temporal sequence for prediction. However, since this is an AI model, new data can be added to the training, the network parameters can be adjusted, and various improvements can be applied to make the system more robust and homogeneous.

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